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BUSINESS INDUSTRY OF WEDDING CATERING

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Abstract: *The current research analyzes business strategy of one of the common fields in restaurant business and service which is considered wedding catering. Moreover, in this work the wedding catering in the world broadly discussed along with some internal and external analysis of the service of catering with some exact examples. The wedding catering marketing is very famous and common in most countries. The marketing analysis is done.*

Key words: *catering, business, marketing, competitors, customer, restaurant.*

A wedding is a celebration for which, as a rule, the closest and dearest people of the bride and groom gather, and for many of them this meeting takes place for the first time, and they are unconsciously divided into "guests from the groom's side" and "guests from the bride's side". It is important to create an atmosphere of unity, one family, but at the same time not to violate the comfort and personal space of each guest. Therefore, it is during the preparation of the wedding that a lot of attention should be paid to the seating of guests.

To date, catering is a very popular service among private corporate customers. The wide possibilities of catering allow you to organize meals at any event, whatever it is and wherever it is held.

We call catering a complex of services for the organization of catering at events. Among such services are the development of a menu in accordance with the wishes of the customer, the preparation of dishes by professional chefs, the delivery of these dishes to the place, table setting, guest service. In simple words, catering is a field kitchen.

We can organize catering anywhere – at home, in the country, in an empty room of a shopping center, a villa, a cottage, a beautiful photo studio.

The most popular direction in catering nowadays is Wedding catering. Many people want to distinguish themselves and organize an unusual wedding. For example, on the roof of a multi-storey building, or on the deck of a ship. And some do not want to sit in a stuffy restaurant hall at all and hold their wedding in the open air.

Wedding catering can be carried out in various formats;

For example; in the form of a banquet, this is the most popular, classic type of weddings. This is a festive feast that can be at home, in the country.

Weddings in the form of a buffet - guests eat standing at high tables or moving around the hall communicating with other guests. Such weddings can be held in any photo studio, in the garden of a beautiful hotel, on the beach. As we know, weddings on the beach are very relevant now and many just dream of spending their most memorable day on their wedding day by the sea, ocean. It's very beautiful and romantic. It will not work to arrange a catering in the form of a banquet there, it can spoil the beautiful atmosphere and therefore, in such cases, catering companies offer a buffet format.

Catering in the format of a picnic, barbecue, it can be a wedding at any outdoor venue.

Wedding catering, like all service sectors, has its own specific features. For example, one of them is seasonality. It is obvious that with the change of the season, the venue of weddings also changes, and therefore their theme.

Wedding catering has developed a lot during COVID19. Almost the entire population of the country was simply afraid of getting infected with the virus and all restaurants were closed, only catering companies worked. Under the strict supervision of the sanitary and epidemiological station. The population began to hold wedding celebrations at home or in the country.

Advantages of wedding catering;

Convenience - young people can not think about anything and do their pre-wedding chores, catering will do everything for them.

Comfort - on the example of a wedding at home. It's so easy and comfortable when a company comes home with its equipment, food, and service personnel. Many people feel

more comfortable at home. In addition, if the house is located far from restaurants from the city center, you can save a lot of time spent on the road.

Decoration is another big plus of wedding catering, the fact that in a restaurant we cannot create the atmosphere that we want to create ourselves. Many restaurants are not even allowed to change anything in their hall.

The ability to make any menu - for example, we are vegetarians and our friends, too, we can choose a menu for ourselves. We know the tastes of our friends very well and can make a suitable menu. Catering will help us in this and when it does not refuse, while the restaurant will not be able to prepare that menu because they have an official, specific menu.

Individuality - when choosing the design and menu. Which is a big plus for many people.

We should add that one of the main advantages of this service is mobility and professional transportation of dishes – for this, catering companies have special equipment (thermal boxes) that will not allow dishes to lose their tastes.

Among the disadvantages of wedding catering, we have considered three main disadvantages;

-Reliability of the company

-Price

-Unpleasant cases

The reliability of the company – A lot of false catering companies which can ruin the wedding evening.

Price- The price differs In some cases can be much more expensive. How? Why? The service comes to your home and arranges a holiday for any of your choices, the price is exceeded due to additional services and transportation costs of the company.

In addition, in some cases, a big difference in price is formed because weddings can be organized far from the city or in another city at all.

Unpleasant cases are such cases as a breakdown of transport, or the company simply forgot about your wedding, the company is not responsible and was late. Just imagine the guests are already here and there is no food.

How to prevent these big cons. The very first rule is not the choice of the menu, but of the catering company itself, you need to choose a company based on reviews if you choose from the Internet or check the qualifications of the administration and then the cook. If the company is located in your city, ask people who have already used the service of this catering company.

We need to make sure that this company will not spoil our wedding evening and will be able to organize the best service.

It is priceless to find the catering that understands the vision, style and taste of the celebration. To create a wedding that is a reflection of the young... Please note that only professional wedding catering will help to leave an unsurpassed aftertaste from the holiday.

What nuances can indicate the complete professionalism of the catering company:

Catering is not only food, but also a comprehensive service. Therefore, the ability to work with the client and pleasant communication of the staff play an important role in choosing a reliable company.

Seasonality of the menu. For example, in the cold season, second courses and hot snacks are more appreciated, in the summer they prefer fruits, chilled drinks, and fresh vegetables.

The presence of uniformed waiters.

Does the customer clearly name how many waiters will serve the event? The trick is that it is not always profitable for management to maintain a large staff of service personnel, especially in regions where the organization of large events rarely happens. Accordingly, waiters are hired for one time, then you definitely should not expect professionalism.

Availability of a table arrangement scheme.

A sufficient number of dishes so that all guests have the same serving.

The firm's solution to the issue of the absence of electricity and water supply on the open site.

Employees have medical books.

Wedding catering is obliged to understand all the nuances and features of a particular wedding (after all, for catering it is a full-fledged exclusive project), to see and offer what the client did not even think about, and to realize the holiday clearly, beautifully and deliciously — all these are the tasks that face wedding catering.

The venue of the banquet always plays a huge role. Under cramped conditions, a person feels uncomfortable and uncomfortable, he rather wants to leave this place. You should think carefully about the site where the celebration will be held. Won't it be too cold or stuffy there? Is there enough room for all the guests so that it is not crowded? Is the furniture provided comfortable? Lack of zest.

The company should differ from its competitors with an interesting and unique offer. So the agency will definitely find its regular customer.

A menu with a bit of exoticism, fresh views on the serving and decor - all this makes the organization memorable. Poor service. Rude waiters spoil the whole impression of the guests, then the customer remains dissatisfied and is unlikely to recommend the company that provided him with catering services to anyone else. The staff should be trained, periodically check their work. There is no place for non-professionals in a self-respecting agency.

Excessive savings. It doesn't make sense to look into the client's wallet and try to make him the cheapest offer possible. A person without money will not apply for the service of organizing an event on the road. Total savings can affect the final result, and this is unprofitable for both sides.

You have the right to ask from wedding catering:

- to enliven your vision of dishes (for example, to serve Caesar salad in a new interpretation
- to help in the selection of a colorful place suitable for your holiday (wedding catering should have a base of locations suitable for the wedding format: chamber, grandiose, thematic);
- create the perfect menu that will suit your taste, with attention to detail, freshness and talent (for example, a halal menu or in the style of your favorite movie, era, color);
- visualize creative alternatives to ensure a flawless wedding dinner (ask to boldly show the visualization of the menu, table decor, uniforms)

What menu can wedding catering offer in contrast to stationary ones?

There are three types of menus:

- a) a ready-made menu that is offered to you in any restaurant,
- b) a menu that will be created "from scratch" for the celebration,
- c) an individual menu that is created together with the newlyweds.

All three types of menus have pros and cons, and it is important that the newlyweds find out which option is acceptable for them.

Sometimes a location (even a stationary restaurant) requires that you use only their kitchen (It is important to take into account: the right of the customer, renting a location for a wedding, to choose the kitchen that they liked - and in 99% of cases, the location does not refuse.)

Not so long ago, catering was a kind of obscure word and did not inspire confidence in most people. Even today, many people believe that the dishes of the exit menu are inferior

to the restaurant in quality and taste. In fact, everything is different: catering has not only equaled, but in many ways surpassed the classic cuisine in the restaurant.

Organizing a wedding banquet, buffet, picnic or cocktail with catering is quite simple. It may not be as familiar as reserving a restaurant yet, but it's certainly more spectacular. An original approach and delicious dishes will make your day special.

A few decades ago, almost no one even knew the word "catering". Today, catering is a separate direction in the field of public catering.

Remember: wedding catering is your personal atelier restaurant

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